

Effects of Drought on Yield and Some Yield Components of Chickpea

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Abstract—This research was conducted to determine responses of chickpeas to drought in different periods (early period, late period, no-irrigation, two times irrigation as control). The trial was made in “Randomized Complete Block Design” with three replications on 2010 and 2011 years in Konya-Turkey. Genotypes were consisted from 7 lines of ICARDA, 2 certified lines and 1 local population. The results showed that; as means of years and genotypes, early period stress showed highest (207.47 kg da⁻¹) seed yield and it was followed by control (202.33 kg da⁻¹), late period (144.64 kg da⁻¹) and normal (106.93 kg da⁻¹) stress applications. The genotypes were affected too much by drought and, the lowest seed was taken from non-irrigated plots. As the means of years and stress applications, the highest (196.01 kg da⁻¹) yield was taken from genotype 22255. The reason of yield variation could be derived from different responses of genotypes to drought.

Keywords—Chickpea, drought, seed yield.

I. INTRODUCTION

WATER is such an important source which plays a role in agriculture and all vital activities [1]. Drought is the most common harmful effect of environment. It cause to reduction in crop production on different parts of the world. Human are not able to or has limits to change ecological conditions, but they are able to recognize some characteristics of plants and also can develop new plant species and regulate or eliminate some of the harmful effects of environment on plant quality parameters for adaptation to different climatic conditions. For this purpose; human tries to find solutions about production systems in agriculture which are more quantitative and qualified. The solutions should be environmentally friendly for sustainable agriculture [2].

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If we know the effects of ecological conditions on plants, the definition and improvement of plant quality parameters will be easy [3]. Increasing of yield could be realized both improving cultivars through plant breeding and improved crop management [4].

Pulse crops are the richest source among plant proteins [5]. Chickpea, one of the pulse crops, is an important source of human food and animal feed; it also helps to improve soil fertility, particularly in dry lands. The entire sown area of chickpea is about 446 218 ha, production and yield are 530 634 t and 1190 kg ha⁻¹, respectively in Turkey [6]. Chickpea is traditionally sown in the spring in the Mediterranean region, so that, the crop encounters heat and drought stress from flower towards maturity and results in low and variable yields. It is required to develop new cultivars which are tolerant to drought.

Biçer and Anlarsal [7] reported that the height of chickpea varies from 16.8 cm to 38.8 cm in chickpea genotypes. It was reported that number of pod varies between 11 and 36 per plant [8]. According to Ceyhan et al. [9] number of seed varies between 26.5 and 31.1 per plant. A previous study showed that, the weight of 1000 seeds ranged from 449.2 to 478.3 g in several genotypes of chickpea. Bakaoğlu and Ayçiçeği [9] reported that biomass varied from 1518 to 2010 kg ha⁻¹ in chickpea. A previous study revealed that seed yield changes from 1215 to 1666 kg ha⁻¹ in chickpea genotypes. Harvest index in chickpea genotypes ranged from 34.4 % to 42.4 % according to Altınbaş and Sepetoğlu [11].

It is well known that, investigating of plant response to drought is needed to develop new species and, plant breeding programs which are property of drought tolerance is necessary to minimize the negative effects of water scarcity. This study was investigated to determination of yield components and identifying the promising chickpea genotypes which were grown under different levels of water shortage.

II. MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research was conducted for two years both during 2010-2011 years in the trial filed of “Research Station for Management of Soil, Water and Desertification” in Konya-Turkey. A total of 10 genotypes which were consisted from 7 chickpea line provided from ICARDA (22112, 22108, 22151, 22202, 22222, 22255 and 22135), 1 local population (Derebucak) and two certified lines (Er-99 and Canitez) were used as control.

The average meteorological data during vegetation period for two years (April, May, June, July and August) as follows: 21.3 °C and 19.2 °C for average temperature, 110.8 mm and

153.2 mm for total rainfall, 45.2 % and 43.1 % for relative humidity respectively. The soil characteristics of research was conducted showed clay loam structure, lower level of organic matter (1.49 %), a higher level of lime (17.14 %) and alkaline (pH=8.40). There was not salinity (0.05 %) problem in the soil, rich content of available potassium (51.60 kg/da) and lower phosphorus (4.01 kg da⁻¹) level.

The trial was conducted in "Randomized Complete Block Design" for both two years with 3 replications and was set up as 4 trials. There was not any irrigation in the first trial (normal conditions), the performance of genotypes were determined with regard to rainfall which depend on the climate. The morphological changes and yields were tried to determine within this natural condition [12]. In the second trial (late period water stress); the maximum yield potential of plants in optimum conditions was determined by none stress application and, irrigation was made during pre-flower and pod set according to climatically conditions. The third trial (early period water stress) was made to investigation the effects of early term drought stress in terms of flowering period. For this purpose, no irrigation was made during flowering period, but the irrigation was made during pod set according to the effective root depth (60 cm) humidity which was determined by gravimetric method, then irrigation was made to complete field capacity [13]. The fourth trial (later period water stress) was made to determine the late period (pod set) drought effect by making irrigation during flowering period to the level of field capacity by determining gravimetric method in effective root (60 cm) depth [13]. For both of two years, sowing was made by hand in the rows with length of 2 m, 50 x 5 cm width of inter row distance, 4-5 cm depth on 01 April 2010 and 04 April 2011 dates. The fertilizer was applied 15 kg da⁻¹ DAP (Diammonium phosphate, 18-46%) for both two years. The hoeing was made for two times to weed and soil ventilation. The harvest was made by hand after the maturing and being yellow colored period of whole plants on plots.

The investigated characteristics in the research were as follows: plant height (cm), number of pod per plant, rate of fertile pod (%), seed per plant, 1000 seed weight (g), biological yield (kg da⁻¹), seed yield (kg da⁻¹) and harvest index (%) respectively [12,13]. Analysis of variance and LSD test was made by using "JUMP" computer based statistical program.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Plant Height

The effects of years on plant height were found important (Table I). The heights of plants in first year (46.07 cm) were found higher than the heights of (43.25 cm) second year (Table II).

The heights of plants showed statistically importance by means of different stress applications (Table I). As the both means of years and genotypes were highest (45.92 cm) in control plots while normal stress applications had the lowest (42.78 cm) height (Table II). Many researchers revealed that the height of plant depend on sowing density, climate and environment conditions besides genetically structure [7,14].

Thus, Pundir and Rajagophan [15] suggested that plant height is effected too much by environmental factors especially soil humidity and mineral content, and also sowing density.

Analysis of variance for plant height among genotypes found important (Table I). As the means of years and stress applications the highest plant height was taken from genotype Derebucak (51.38 cm), while 22135 showed the lowest (34.38 cm) plant height (Table III). The similar results were found previously [7,8,9,10,11,14].

B. Number of Pod

Number of pod per plant in first year (29.08) were higher than number of pod per plant (25.28) in second year (Table 2). As the means of years and genotypes, the highest (29.53) value was in control plots while late period stress application had the lowest (22.55) value for number of pod per plant (Table 3). Kumar et al. (1981) reported that number of pod per plant was varied from 12 to 256 and it was affected too much by environmental factors.

As the means of years and stress applications the highest value was taken from genotype 22222 (33.29 number), while 22255 showed the lowest (23.46) pod per plant. The other genotypes which were used in the research showed their values between these intervals (Table 3). The other researchers found similar results for number of pod per plant [7,8,9].

C. Rate of Fertile Pod

The rate of fertile pod showed a rate of 83.08 % in first year and 78.46 % in the second year. As the means of years and genotypes, the highest (84.09 %) rate was in control plots while normal stress application had the lowest (77.78 %) rate for number of fertile pod (Table III). According to the results of variance analysis for fertile pod rate among genotypes found important statistically (Table I). The rates of fertile pods were changed between 72.78 (22255) and 85.84% (22202) among genotypes (Table III). The results of the research showed accordance with Lepore et al. [13]'s results.

D. Number of Seed per Plant

As the both means of years and genotypes were highest (32.53) in control plots while late stress applications had the lowest (25.55) seed per plant (Table III). Seed number per plant was varied from 25.33 (Canitez and 22255) to 35.08 (22222) in genotypes. For number of seed per plant, the interaction of genotypes x stress applications was found statistically important according to variance analysis (Table I). The highest (43.83) value was taken from 22222 on control plots and, the lowest (16.00) value was taken from Er-99 genotype on normal stress application (Table 3). The results of the study were compatible with Ceyhan et al. [9] and Altunbaş and Sepetoğlu [11]'s outcomes.

E. Thousand Seed Weight

The effects of years on 1000 seed weight were found important (Table I). The values in first year (400.90 g) were found higher than the values of (374.65 g) second year. For 1000 seed weight, the variations of genotypes that were used

in the trial were found statistically important in terms of the different stress applications (Table 1). As the both means of years and genotypes, the highest (429.11 g) value was in normal stress application while late period stress application had the lowest (371.80 g) value for 1000 seed weight (Table 2). According to the results of variance analysis among genotypes for 1000 seed weight found statistically important (Table I).

The weights were varied between 348.02 g (22222) and 431.89 g (22108) for 1000 seeds (Table 3). The variance analysis which was made for 1000 seed weight was found as statistically important for genotypes x stress applications interactions (Table I). The highest (498.63 g) value was taken from 22108 genotype on normal stress application while late period stress application had the lowest (269.80 g) value of genotype 22222. The previous findings for 1000 seed weight had been found in accordance with these results [7,8,9,11].

TABLE I
MEANS SQUARES OF INVESTIGATED CHARACTERISTICS IN CHICKPEA GENOTYPES UNDER DIFFERENT LEVELS OF DROUGHT

Sources	DF	Plant height	Number of pod	Rate of fertile pod	Number of seed per plant
Replication	2	24.2792	284.788	378.925	318.987
Year (Y)	1	476.017**	866.4	1277.48*	1113.7
Error ₁	2	0.70417	224.788	85.3868	214.154
Stress Applications (SA)	3	106.494**	602.161	572.86	805.015
Y X SA Interaction	3	0.82778	428.278*	1081.98**	601.026**
Error ₂	6	4.00694	206.949	148.757	217.449
Genotype (G)	9	1053.4**	221.128	391.092**	223.43
Y X G Interaction	9	0.48889	71.7333	53.0992	70.7597
SA X G Interaction	27	3.81235	418.791**	330.802**	417.17**
Y X SA X G Interaction	27	0.74444	63.5247	36.2474	60.6745
Error ₃	150	2.987	284.788	89.837	147.709

Sources	DF	1000 Seed weight	Biological yield	Seed yield	Harvest index
Replication	2	3063.41	115866	1048.9	902.098
Year (Y)	1	38327**	460107*	119852**	660.116
Error ₁	2	304.491	16547.8	90.1913	47.2296
Stress Applications (SA)	3	44940*	252314**	139671**	2448.7900
Y X SA Interaction	3	167.851	199282**	62573.6**	564.441**
Error ₂	6	5821.22	14644.9	4480.66	423.451
Genotype (G)	9	21494.8**	42506**	12080.8**	379.83900
Y X G Interaction	9	97.6684	7566.82	1372.39	40.3583
SA X G Interaction	27	8989.52**	24131.7**	5782.77**	262.379**
Y X SA X G Interaction	27	152.73	7948.31	1684.35	59.2998
Error ₃	150	3836.45	10449.1	1708.1	94.223

* $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$

TABLE II
MEANS OF INVESTIGATED CHARACTERISTICS BY YEARS IN CHICKPEA GENOTYPES UNDER DIFFERENT LEVELS OF STRESS APPLICATIONS

Genotypes	Plant height		Number of pod		Rate of fertile pod		Number of seed per plant	
	2010	2011	2010	2011	2010	2011	2010	2011
22108	47.67	44.67	28.08	22.92	84.53	78.52	30.25	24.50
22112	52.08	49.67	25.08	25.25	83.48	81.77	27.17	26.58
22135	35.75	33.00	35.08	24.83	85.46	80.03	37.17	26.58
22151	51.17	48.25	30.42	26.08	82.01	75.97	32.67	27.83
22202	41.67	39.08	30.83	26.58	86.39	85.29	32.92	28.42
22222	51.17	48.25	33.17	33.42	84.00	83.55	35.08	35.08
22255	42.25	39.42	26.42	20.50	77.92	67.64	28.58	22.08
Canitez	35.75	33.25	26.92	20.08	77.63	72.45	29.08	21.58
Derebucak	53.08	49.67	27.17	26.67	84.15	80.62	29.17	28.08
Er-99	50.08	47.25	27.58	26.42	85.23	78.82	29.83	28.08
Mean	46.07	43.25	29.08	25.28	83.08	78.46	31.19	26.88

Genotypes	1000 Seed weight		Biological yield		Seed yield		Harvest index	
	2010	2011	2010	2011	2010	2011	2010	2011
22108	443.35	420.43	516.67	423.33	214.45	148.20	44.17	36.73
22112	410.24	384.99	435.83	380.00	204.91	156.87	47.46	41.15
22135	404.33	379.49	520.00	387.92	189.24	144.90	39.21	37.60
22151	418.62	399.49	480.00	387.08	187.67	151.43	39.01	39.60
22202	368.84	342.26	490.42	398.89	200.63	146.17	39.59	34.57
22222	364.73	331.31	592.08	435.83	201.68	137.05	33.21	30.75
22255	387.63	360.18	490.42	447.64	207.42	184.60	42.79	42.72
Canitez	359.23	339.14	450.42	360.00	186.94	134.97	42.08	38.77
Derebucak	426.04	399.38	412.71	346.80	135.22	105.61	35.68	30.94
Er-99	426.03	399.62	415.21	360.56	148.75	120.17	36.51	33.73
Mean	400.90	375.63	480.38	392.81	187.69	143.00	39.97	36.65

TABLE III
MEANS AND LDS VALUES OF INVESTIGATED CHARACTERISTICS IN CHICKPEA GENOTYPES UNDER DIFFERENT LEVELS OF STRESS APPLICATIONS

Genotypes	Plant height					Number of pod				
	Normal	Late	Early	Control	Mean	Normal	Late	Early	Control	Mean
22108	44.50	46.67	47.17	46.33	46.17	26.67	19.17	35.33	20.83	25.50
22112	49.00	51.17	51.17	52.17	50.88	31.67	19.83	14.33	34.83	25.17
22135	32.67	33.67	34.50	36.67	34.38	33.17	19.00	21.17	46.50	29.96
22151	47.83	49.67	50.17	51.17	49.71	30.50	13.67	43.00	25.83	28.25
22202	37.50	40.33	42.33	41.33	40.38	31.33	22.17	24.83	36.50	28.71
22222	47.17	50.67	49.17	51.83	49.71	27.17	31.67	33.50	40.83	33.29
22255	38.67	42.17	40.67	41.83	40.83	19.50	31.00	20.83	22.50	23.46
Camtez	33.00	34.83	35.67	34.50	34.50	34.00	19.33	23.83	16.83	23.50
Derebucak	50.00	51.33	51.67	52.50	51.38	26.50	20.00	33.00	28.17	26.92
Er-99	47.50	47.83	48.50	50.83	48.67	17.17	29.67	38.67	22.50	27.00
Mean	42.78	44.83	45.10	45.92	44.66	27.77	22.55	28.85	29.53	27.18
LSD _{SA} : 1.355; LSD _G : 1.302					LSD _{SAXG} : 25.42					
Genotypes	Rate of fertile pod					Number of seed per plant				
	Normal	Late	Early	Control	Mean	Normal	Late	Early	Control	Mean
22108	79.32	77.34	89.32	80.12	81.52	25.17	22.17	38.33	23.83	27.38
22112	83.66	84.85	70.37	91.62	82.62	29.50	22.83	17.33	37.83	26.88
22135	79.61	73.02	86.66	91.69	82.74	31.83	22.00	24.17	49.50	31.88
22151	79.49	70.18	88.91	77.38	78.99	29.50	16.67	46.00	28.83	30.25
22202	82.24	82.02	87.20	91.90	85.84	30.17	25.17	27.83	39.50	30.67
22222	79.46	80.14	84.74	90.74	83.77	25.33	34.67	36.50	43.83	35.08
22255	59.66	85.27	66.21	79.99	72.78	18.00	34.00	23.83	25.50	25.33
Camtez	83.78	76.81	74.38	65.18	75.04	32.33	22.33	26.83	19.83	25.33
Derebucak	78.33	73.97	91.25	85.97	82.38	24.33	23.00	36.00	31.17	28.63
Er-99	72.23	81.76	87.79	86.31	82.03	16.00	32.67	41.67	25.50	28.96
Mean	77.78	78.54	82.68	84.09	80.77	26.22	25.55	31.85	32.53	29.04
LSD _G : 7.139; LSD _{SAXG} : 14.28					LSD _{SAXG} : 18.31					
Genotypes	1000 Seed weight					Biological yield				
	Normal	Late	Early	Control	Mean	Normal	Late	Early	Control	Mean
22108	498.63	390.77	403.10	435.07	431.89	399.03	474.72	537.50	468.75	470.00
22112	431.17	381.30	426.07	351.93	397.62	306.67	403.06	514.31	407.64	407.92
22135	408.63	370.30	387.27	401.43	391.91	306.11	470.84	608.34	430.56	453.96
22151	412.12	421.97	361.00	441.13	409.05	336.39	528.33	354.86	514.58	433.54
22202	413.87	345.50	344.17	318.67	355.55	278.20	458.06	489.58	552.78	444.65
22222	423.17	269.80	345.00	354.10	348.02	371.94	484.58	553.47	645.83	513.96
22255	368.20	408.70	398.53	320.20	373.91	367.36	482.92	462.64	563.19	469.03
Camtez	468.80	355.93	272.37	299.63	349.18	367.22	398.06	413.89	441.67	405.21
Derebucak	446.00	417.57	379.83	407.43	412.71	370.00	462.22	360.42	326.39	379.76
Er-99	420.50	422.13	420.13	388.53	412.83	299.31	416.39	392.09	443.75	387.88
Mean	429.11	378.40	373.75	371.81	388.27	340.22	457.92	468.71	479.51	436.59
LSD _{SA} : 34.09; LSD _G : 46.45; LSD _{SAXG} : 93.30					LSD _{SA} : 81.91; LSD _G : 76.99; LSD _{SAXG} : 154.0					
Genotypes	Seed yield					Harvest index				
	Normal	Late	Early	Control	Mean	Normal	Late	Early	Control	Mean
22108	107.77	146.41	269.76	201.34	181.32	29.96	36.39	51.09	44.36	40.45
22112	107.57	171.07	200.55	244.38	180.89	35.90	42.80	39.05	59.46	44.30
22135	83.06	153.42	213.26	218.55	167.07	30.06	35.63	36.53	51.41	38.41
22151	90.86	158.99	184.33	244.01	169.55	27.77	30.22	50.44	48.78	39.30
22202	71.29	165.37	235.80	221.14	173.40	24.10	35.80	48.49	39.92	37.08
22222	91.80	138.95	202.55	244.16	169.37	25.21	29.41	35.88	37.44	31.98
22255	157.81	148.94	273.31	203.98	196.01	42.45	31.09	59.50	37.97	42.75
Camtez	141.60	129.91	198.05	174.26	160.95	40.87	33.71	47.41	39.72	40.42
Derebucak	124.59	117.15	121.83	118.11	120.42	36.68	26.70	33.04	36.83	33.31
Er-99	92.97	116.19	175.30	153.39	134.46	33.61	27.73	43.82	35.31	35.12
Mean	106.93	144.64	207.47	202.33	165.34	32.66	32.95	44.52	43.12	38.31
LSD _{SA} : 45.31; LSD _G : 31.13; LSD _{SAXG} : 62.25					LSD _{SAXG} : 14.62					

F. Biological Yield

The effects of years on biological yield were found important (Table 1). Biological yield in first year was determined 480.38 kg da⁻¹ and 392.81 kg da⁻¹ in second year (Table 2). For biological yield, the variations of genotypes showed statistically importance in terms of the different stress applications (Table 1). As the both means of years and genotypes, the variations were measured between 340.22 kg da⁻¹ (normal stress application) and 479.51 kg da⁻¹ (control stress application) for biological yield (Table II).

Analysis of variance showed there were differences among the genotypes in terms of biological yield (Table 1). As the means of years and stress applications, the highest biological yield was taken from genotype 22222 (513.96 kg da⁻¹) and the lowest (379.76 kg da⁻¹) amount was taken from genotype Derebucak (Table 3). The interaction of genotypes x stress applications which was calculated for biological yield was found important as statistically (Table 1). The highest (645.83 kg da⁻¹) value was taken from 22222 on control period stress application, and normal stress application had the lowest

(278.20 kg da⁻¹) value in which genotype 22202. The results of study were similar to the previously studies which were made by other researchers [12,16].

G.Seed Yield

Effects of the years showed statistically importance on seed yield (Table 1). The amount in first year (187.69 kg da⁻¹) was higher than the amount of (143.00 kg da⁻¹) the second year (Table 2).

For seed yield, the variations of genotypes showed statistically importance in terms of the different stress applications (Table 1). As the both means of years and genotypes, the early period stress applied plots showed the highest (207.47 kg da⁻¹) value. The other stress applications were followed as respectively; control (202.33 kg da⁻¹), late period (144.64 kg da⁻¹) and normal (106.93 kg da⁻¹) by the perspective of seed yield (Table 3). Many researchers implicated that seed yield is effected too much by climate and environment conditions [7, 9, 13]. Furthermore, Toker and Çağırın [12] obtained specified that seed yield of chickpeas was decreased significantly in drought conditions. The present study showed the lowest seed yield from the non-irrigated plots.

As the means of years and stress applications, the highest seed yield was taken from genotype 22135 (211.01 kg da⁻¹) and the lowest (135.42 kg da⁻¹) value was taken from genotype 22112 (Table 3). For seed yield, the interaction of genotypes x stress applications was found statistically important in variance analysis (Table 1). The highest (273.31 kg da⁻¹) value was taken from genotype 22255 in early period stress application and, the lowest (71.29 kg da⁻¹) value was taken from genotype 22202 in normal stress application (Table 3). The reason why genotypes showed difference in their seed yield could be explained by genetically difference and effecting different with respect to years [12, 13]. The results of present study showed similarity with previously reported data [7,8,9,10,11,12].

H.Harvest Index

Effects of the years showed statistically importance on harvest index (Table 1). Harvest index in first year was determined 39.97% and 36.65% in second year (Table 2). As the both means of years and genotypes, the highest (44.52%) value was taken from early period stress applied plots and, normal stress application had the lowest (32.66%) value for harvest index (Table 3).

Harvest index values were varied from 33.31% (Derebucak) to 44.30 (22112) in chickpea genotypes. For harvest index, the interaction of genotypes x stress applications was found statistically important according to variance analysis (Table 1). The highest (59.46%) value was taken from genotype 22112 in control stress application and, the lowest (24.10%) value was taken from genotype 22202 in normal stress application. The data which collected for harvest index were similar with previously results [8, 11].

IV. CONCLUSION

Consequently, the more drought-resistant genotypes: 22155, Derebucak and Canitez are the promising genotypes for seed yield and some agricultural characteristics.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. Önder, E. Ceyhan and A. Kahraman, "Effects of Agricultural Practices on Environment," *Biology, Environment and Chemistry (ICBEC 2011)*, Volume 24, Page 28-32, December 28-30, Dubai, UAE, 2011.
- [2] A. Kahraman, M. Önder and E. Ceyhan, "Biodiversity and Biosecurity in Turkey," *Biology, Environment and Chemistry (ICBEC 2011)*, Volume 24, Page 33-37, December 28-30, Dubai, UAE, 2011.
- [3] E. Ceyhan, A. Kahraman and M. Önder, "Environmental Effects on Quality Parameters of Plant Products", *Biology, Environment and Chemistry (ICBEC 2011)*, Volume 24, Page 23-27, December 28-30, Dubai, UAE, 2011.
- [4] K. E. McPhee and F.J. Muehlbauer, "Biomass Production and Related Characters in the Core Collection of *Pisum* Germplasm. *Genetic Resources and Crop Evaluation*, 48: 195-203, 2001.
- [5] M. Önder and A. Kahraman, "Antinutritional Factors in Food Grain Legumes", *1st International Symposium on Sustainable Development*, volume 3, page 40-44, June 8-10, Sarajevo, 2009.
- [6] Anonymous, 2012. <http://faostat.fao.org>
- [7] B.T. Biçer and A.E. Anlarsal, "Bazı Nohut (*Cicer arietinum* L) Köy Çeşitlerinde Bitkisel ve Tarımsal Özelliklerin Belirlenmesi", *Ankara Üniversitesi Ziraat Fakültesi Dergisi*, 10 (4), 389-396, 2004.
- [8] E. Öztaş, B. Bucak, V. Al and A. Kahraman, "Farklı Nohut (*Cicer arietinum* L.) Çeşitlerinin Harran Ovası Koşullarında Kışa Dayanıklılık, Verim ve Diğer Özelliklerinin Belirlenmesi" *Hr.Ü.Z.F.Dergisi*, 11 (3/4):81- 85, 2007.
- [9] E.Ceyhan, M. Onder, M. Harmankaya, M. Hamurcu, and S. Gezgin, "Response of Chickpea Cultivars to Application of Boron in Boron – Deficient Calcareous Soils", *Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis*, 38:17, 2381-2399, 2007.
- [10] A. Bakaoğlu and M. Ayçiçeği, "Bingöl Ekolojik Koşullarında Bazı Nohut (*Cicer arietinum* L) Çeşitlerinin Verim ve Verim Öğeleri Üzerine Bir Araştırma", *F. Ü. Fen Ve Mühendislik Bilimleri Dergisi*, 17 (1), 107-113, 2002.
- [11] M. Altunbaş and H. Sepetoğlu, "Yeni Geliştirilen Nohut Hatlarının Bornova Koşullarında Verim ve Bazı Tarımsal Özellikleri Üzerinde Araştırmalar", *Ege Üniv. Ziraat Fak. Derg.*, 38 (2-3):39-46, 2001.
- [12] C. Toker and M.İ. Çağırın, "Assessment of Response to Drought Stress of Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) Lines under Rainfed Conditions", *Tr. J of Agriculture and Forestry*, 22(6):615-621, 1998.
- [13] L. Lepout, N.C. Turner, S.L. Davies and K.H.M. Siddique, "Variation in Pod Production and abortion Among Chickpea Cultivars under Terminal Drought", *Europ. J. Agronomy*, 24: 236–246, 2006.
- [14] P.N. Bahl, D.P. Raju, J. Kumar, and S.S. Yadav, "Pusa 267 A New High Yielding Kabulu Gram", *Plant Breeding Abstracts*, 61(7): 862p, 1991.
- [15] R.P.S. Pundir and C.K. Rajagopalan, "Collection of Chickpea Germplasm in Timil Nadu", *India Plant Breeding Abstracts*, (58): 391, 1988.
- [16] S. Jana and K.B. Singh, "Evidence of Geographical Divergence in Kabuli Chickpea from Germplasm Evaluation Data", *Crop Sci*, 33: 626-632, 1993.